

Dual Probabilities, One for Particle Number, Another for Kinematics?

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For the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution one has a single probability, namely $C \exp(-e/T)$. In this note, we argue that for the case of fermions and bosons there are two probabilities. The first probability, $f(e_i/T)$, describes the number of particles in energy state e_i (or a particle number probability). The second, we argue, is related to two particle scattering which establishes the equilibrium in the first place. For the MB case, the scattering probability is the same as one uses $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ for the elastic collision $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. For the fermion case, there is a restriction, namely that e_1 cannot scatter into e_3 if it is occupied and e_2 into e_4 if it is occupied. The same considerations apply to the time reversed reaction. For the boson case, e_1 scattering into e_3 is enhanced by n_3+1 and e_2 by n_4+1 . Thus, if one tries to write fermion and boson scattering in the form: $g(e_1)g(e_2)=g(e_3)g(e_4)$ such that $\ln(g(e_i)) = (e_i-u)/T$ where u is the chemical potential, one obtains a new probability $g(e_i)$. Following Kaniadakis (1), one may write $k(f(e_i)) = g(e_i)$.

One may use the “second” probability $g(e_i)$ to obtain the average number of particles in state e_1 , namely $f(e_1)$ the “first probability” which is either the Fermi-Dirac distribution or the Bose-Einstein distribution. This, we argue, is what the usual grand canonical partition function calculation obtains. In other words, the grand canonical partition function approach is a basic averaging approach (using average total energy and average total particle number) using $g(e_i)$ as the basic single particle probability. The grand canonical partition function calculation uses the second probability $g(e_i)$ in the same manner in which Shannon’s macrostate probability calculations use $f(i)$. (2)

Two Particle Elastic Scattering as the Physical Basis Behind Equilibrium

We have argued in previous notes, that one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) distributions directly from a time reversed balance of two body elastic scattering reactions implementing appropriate restrictions or enhancements which may arise. There seems to be no need for counting states, entropy or its maximization in such an approach. In fact, kinematics are essential for determining the equilibrium.

For the MB case, one has for the reaction $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1))$$

Taking \ln of both sides of ((1)) and equating to the conservation of energy yields the MB distribution. For the FD case, e_1 may only scatter into e_3 if it is empty and e_2 into e_4 if it is empty. The probability e_2 is empty is $1-f(e_3)$ and e_4 empty $1-f(e_4)$. Thus, one may use four “and” conditions for the LHS of ((1)) i.e. for the presence of e_1 , the presence of e_2 , the absence of a particle in e_3 and the absence of a particle in e_4 . A similar argument holds for the time reversed reaction, thus:

$$f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)]f(e_2)[1-f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1-f(e_1)]f(e_4)[1-f(e_2)] \quad ((2))$$

Writing as: $f(e_1)/[1-f(e_1)] f(e_2)/[1-f(e_2)] = f(e_3)/[1-f(e_3)] f(e_4)/[1-f(e_4)]$ ((2a)) and taking ln of both sides and equating to $-(e_i-u)/T$ yields the FD distribution.

For the boson case, there is an enhancement. The probability for e_1 to scatter into e_3 is enhanced by n_3+1 where n_3 is the number of bosons in the e_3 state. Representing this as a probability one has $f(e_3)+1$ thus:

$$f(e_1)[1+f(e_3)]f(e_2)[1+f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1+f(e_1)]f(e_4)[1+f(e_2)] \quad ((3))$$

Writing $f(e_1)/[1+f(e_1)] f(e_2)/[1+f(e_2)] = f(e_3)/[1+f(e_3)] f(e_4)/[1+f(e_4)]$ ((3a)) and taking ln of both sides and equating to $-(e_i-u)/T$ yields the BE equation.

For a more general problem, one may postulate as Kaniadakis (1) that the kinematics time reversed balance is of the form:

$$k(f(e_1)) k(f(e_2)) = k(f(e_3)) k(f(e_4)) \quad ((4)) \text{ where } k \text{ is a function.}$$

Taking the ln of ((4)) and equating to $-(e_i-u)/T$ (conservation of energy) yields the result:

$$\ln(k(f(e_i))) = -(e_i-u)/T \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{Thus, } k(f(e_i)) = \exp(-(e_i-u)/T) \quad ((6)).$$

This, we argue, is a new independent second probability.

A New Probability?

For the MB, FD and BE case, as well as more general cases, one wishes to know $f(e_i/T)$ i.e. the probability to have a particle with a certain energy. This may then be used to calculate total overall energy $E = \sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ and other averages.

For the general case, however, we argue there is a second probability in the problem, namely ((6)) related to the time balanced elastic reaction. We argue this is the "driver" of the equilibrium. ((6)) allows one to write the independent "and" probability statement ((4)). Thus, one begins with the independent probability $k(f(e_i))$ and tries to calculate the average number of particles in a state e_i . This average number, however, becomes a probability itself, because it is related to the probability to have a particle in state e_i .

Thus, for the FD case, one may only have 1 or 0 particles in state e_i so:

$$f(e_i)_{FD} = \text{Ave number of particles in } e_i \text{ FD} = \frac{[1 \exp(-(e_i-u)/T)^1 + 0 \exp(-(e_i-u)/T)^0]}{[\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)^1 + \exp(-(e_i-u)/T)^0]} \quad ((7))$$

As shown above $\exp(-(e_i-u)/T) = g(e_i) = k(f(e_i))$.

((7)) yields the FD distribution.

It should be noted that ((7)) is exactly the result obtained from the usual grand canonical Partition function approach i.e.

$$f(e_i)_{FD} = d/du \ln \{ \exp(-0(e-u)/T) + \exp(-(e-u)/T) \} \quad ((7c))$$

The grand canonical partition function approach is promoted as an approximate counting scheme, but it uses the “built in” single particle probabilities $\exp(-(e-u)/T)$. These follow from the overall idea that a macrostate with total energy E and number of particles N has a weight: $\exp(-(E-uN)/T)$. We argue one does not need to think in terms of the counting of macrostates, but rather ultimately uses an “independent” single particle probability (from scattering) of $\exp(-(e-u)/T)$.

For the boson case, one may have any number of particles in a state e_i i.e.

$$f(e_i)_{BE} = \frac{\{\text{Sum over } i \quad i [\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)]^i\}}{\{\text{Sum over } i [\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)]^i\}} \quad ((8))$$

((8)) yields the BE distribution.

Again, in the grand canonical partition function approach, one introduces macrostates with weights of $\exp(-(E-uN)/T)$ which yields “single particle weights” of $[\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)]^i$. Thus, there is a “second probability” in the problem, an independent probability given by: $[\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)]$. From this second probability, one calculates the first probability, namely $f(e_i)$. We argue the second probability really comes from restrictions or enhancements introduced into the time reversal balanced elastic reaction equation.

It should be noted that the “independent second probability” used to calculate the FD and BE distributions matches Shannon’s independent probability exactly (with $f(e_i)$ replaced with $g(e_i)$ i.e.

$$P \text{ macrostate Shannon} = \text{Product over } i \quad f_i^{N_i} \quad ((9)) \quad (\text{from } (2))$$

Thus, for generalized cases, $f(e_i)$ is not an independent probability which may be used as in the MB case to describe a time reversal balanced elastic two body reaction, rather one needs a new probability $g(e_i)$ such that $g(e_1)g(e_2) = g(e_3)g(e_4)$. From there one calculates the first probability $f(e_i)$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue again that one may obtain $f(e_i)$, the probability for a particle to be in the energy state e_i , by using only a time reversal balanced elastic two body equation. No counting or entropy is needed. There may, however, be restrictions or enhancements involved in this balance equation. Thus, following the MB case, one tries to write an independent probability equation of the form:

$$g(e_1)g(e_2) = g(e_3)g(e_4)$$

This introduces a second probability into the problem namely $g(e_i)$. This is an independent probability and may be used to calculate the “average” number of particles in state e_i , namely:

$$f(e_i) = \text{ave number of particles in } e_i = \frac{[\text{Sum over } i \quad e_i g(e_i)]}{[\text{Sum over } i \quad g(e_i)]}$$

Furthermore $g(e_i) = k(f(e_i)) = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$ where k is a function. Thus, $\exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$ becomes the new independent probability.

We argue this is essentially the approach used in the grand canonical partition function calculation of $f(e_i)$

. Thus, the grand canonical partition function “sneaks” in a second probability $\exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$ in order to calculate $f(e_i)$.

References

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